

Classroom Procedures Contribute To The Activation Of Teaching Methods

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Abstract:

Modern education calls for diversification in teaching methods to provide educational content in order to provide learners with several educational experiences to show their effects on them as an outcome of the educational process , and to achieve this , the teacher should follow teaching methods commensurate with the nature of the subject , educational goals and the level of learners , and also correspond to the characteristics and experience of the and the factors that contribute to its activation in order to bring about the desired learning among students.

These classroom procedures are what the current research will address, so that they can help the teacher to successfully perform his educational task.

Keywords: teaching methods, lecture method, dialogue and discussion method, survey method, problem solving method, brainstorming method, project method

Introduction

Modern education seeks to develop the skills of learners to think , investigate, research and creativity, and this has increased the need to employ various modern educational methods in order to create a compatibility between the needs of learners and the professional competencies of the teacher in order to keep pace with rapid civilizational changes.

One of these educational methods; teaching methods that are effective tools in the educational process- learning in general and in dealing with scientific material in particular and irreplaceable because without a teaching method adopted by the teacher, the pedagogical goals of the lesson cannot be achieved.

The teaching methods determined by the teacher must depend on some important foundations and criteria; such as the nature of the scientific subject , educational goals , the academic stage of the learners , as well as the teacher's scientific experience that will help him to make the classroom situation a success , so it is necessary that the teacher assumes several appropriate classroom roles when implementing the teaching methods that he will choose, taking into account some considerations and factors that contribute to their activation in order to bring about the desired learning among his students, the teacher's role is no longer limited to transferring knowledge and information to the minds of learners , But this went beyond directing learners taking into account their nature and Individual Differences , and so the teaching process has become the art of making learning happen , and the various roles and classroom procedures of the teacher represent his professional behavioral patterns that he performs to guide learners to carry out educational activities through which they obtain information themselves by interacting with appropriate educational situations, and this is done by determining an appropriate teaching method that helps achieve the educational goals set by the teacher .

the concept of teaching methods:

Teaching methods are one of the classroom procedures determined by the teacher in his lesson planning and contribute to the success of the educational situation , they play a fundamental and important role in dealing with the scientific material and in the organization of the lesson , and are a necessary and effective tool to achieve general and special educational goals.

It is also defined as the approach taken by the teacher to communicate the knowledge , information , skills and activities stated in the textbook or curriculum to the learner easily and conveniently , so that the teaching method ensures this interaction between the teacher and the students, and between the students and the course material ... All this aims to bring about a relatively permanent positive change in the behavior of the learner (Afnan Darwaza , 2000 , p.176).

The teaching methods also represent the set of steps that the teacher sets and follows in order to deliver the scientific material to the students using the available methods and means, provided that these methods are responsive and consistent with the nature of the scientific material, the nature of the students, their behavioral characteristics, their psychological formation and the factors of the surrounding environment .(Radina Yusuf et al., 2005, p. 54).

From this it becomes clear that teaching methods are a set of pedagogical methods performed by the teacher in order to deliver knowledge and information to students in a way that ensures interaction among them and achieves the desired learning , provided that these methods are compatible with the criteria for their selection.

criteria for the selection of teaching methods:

The choice of any method of teaching depends on the extent to which it is preferred by the teacher , but this is determined by criteria that must be taken into account when making a decision to choose or prefer one teaching method over another.

One of these criteria is the following : (Mohammed Ziad Hamdan , 1999 , pp. 127-131).

the nature of the educational goal:

Each educational subject is associated with a number of educational and behavioral goals; for example , if the goal is Cognitive , the teacher may use a cognitive teaching method such as a lecture and questions , but if the goal is of an emotional and value nature , the teaching method is either of the kind that allows interaction between the teacher and students , and students with each other; such problems. ...

The teacher should look at the nature of the educational goal , and then choose the appropriate teaching method to teach what he wants.

. the nature of the study material:

The choice of teaching method depends on the nature of the subject matter , and the teacher must be aware of this and have a sufficient background in this field in order to succeed in teaching and communicating knowledge to the minds of his students , he may rely on the method of discussion to teach social subjects of various kinds , or adopt direct teaching methods (such as description , presentation , lecture , delivery...) To teach academic subjects for which information is the main goal of their education.

save time to achieve the educational goal:

The factor that should be taken into account when choosing the appropriate teaching method is the time factor , if time is available , the most appropriate teaching methods are those in which the teacher interacts with the learner (such as discussion so that each one shares his opinions and observations), but if time is tight, the teacher resorts to the lecture method and gives the learners some time for questions and discussion from time to time.

the number of learners in the class:

The number of learners in the classroom determines the appropriate teaching method .if the number of learners is from five to twenty-five , it is preferable to use the discussion to exchange experiences and vaccinate opinions , but if the number of learners ranges from twenty-one to forty students, the lecture becomes the most successful and time-saving teaching method.

the academic stage or chronological age of the learners:

Taking into account the stage of study or the chronological age of learners is a necessary thing that schools should take into account when choosing a teaching method .higher education students are suited to the method of lecture or discussion , unlike primary school students, who are suited to the method of description, presentation and representation with the use of appropriate means of illustration so that the teacher ensures effective and effective learning among his students.

teaching aids:

The lack of good and diverse educational means prevents the use of certain methods , so the lack of means leads to the disruption of the efforts of a successful teacher , but the availability of means and their diversity may not lead to good use of them because the use of means in teaching well is closely related to the personality of the teacher and the extent of his conviction in his work and the level of preparation before joining the profession (Abu Taleb Saeed et al., 2001 , pp. 109-110).

external readings and original sources:

The availability of external readings-whether for the teacher or the student-or access to the original sources makes the teacher able to use certain methods and techniques in teaching a subject that he cannot use if it is not available , and this shows the importance of the university library and the books , references and magazines it contains (Abdul Khalik et al., 2007, p. 52).

Therefore , the teacher should take note of these criteria when choosing one of the teaching methods , as the success of his teaching depends on the success of choosing the appropriate teaching method for the nature of the educational goal , the nature of the subject , the time available , in addition to the number of learners in the classroom and the academic stage to which they belong, as well as the availability of teaching aids and research sources.

types of teaching methods:

There are many teaching methods that a teacher can adopt in achieving educational goals, and any teaching method can be effective in a particular educational - learning situation and ineffective in another situation, but it depends on the teacher's experience and creativity in choosing the appropriate one for the planned educational - learning situation.

The following is a discussion of some commonly used teaching methods, identifying the classroom roles of the teacher and some of the considerations and factors contributing to the activation of these methods, from which the teacher can benefit.

lecture method:

It is a teaching method in which the teacher addresses a large group of learners, it is very similar to the method of diction, which is an oral presentation in which the listener is not allowed to ask a question during the lecture, but rather after its completion .(Afnan Darwaza , 2000, p.185).

This method is considered one of the most widely used methods at the level of university education; the professor delivers and explains the lecture to students on a specific topic or field, and the role of students is limited to listening and taking notes of lectures. (Rudeina Yusuf and others, 2005, p.77).

The role of the teacher in the lecture method:

According to this method, the teacher throws information to the learners, and this requires following the following classroom procedures:

The task is to determine how much information he will display.

The task of organizing this information in the form of consecutive and graduated paragraphs according to the logical organization of the material.

The task is to explain and interpret each paragraph according to its degree of difficulty.

The teacher uses teaching aids, such as: a blackboard, showing a picture, a map, or some models, relying on diction and verbal expression on his part.

It is necessary to ask some questions after explaining each paragraph or at the end of the lesson, so that the teacher makes sure that the learners understand what he explained.

In this case, the teacher should take into account some considerations to activate the lecture method, including:

The teacher should practice arranging his ideas when preparing the lesson, and identify the topics that need to be presented with examples or applications.

To arouse the interest of learners in the lesson, and increase their motivation using the appropriate preparation.

The teacher should be interested in following the learners during the explanation by raising some questions during the lesson, which reduces the impact of distractions and distractions of learners from the subject of the lesson.

The teacher should use teaching aids of various types, which contributes to taking into account the individual differences between learners, and attracts their attention to the subject of the lesson.

The teacher should make sure that his pronunciation of the words is clear, and his voice is audible, and that he diversifies and changes the tones of his voice to emphasize important points and prevent the distraction of learners ' attention.

The teacher should change his position inside the classroom, and move purposefully during the explanation, which reduces the boredom resulting from using the lecture method.

method of dialogue and discussion:

This method is based on a dialogue between the teacher and students in the form of questions or discussions, through which students progress towards achieving certain goals or objectives, and therefore it is called the dialogue method or the discussion method.

The role of the teacher in the method of dialogue and discussion:

According to this method, the teacher performs a set of classroom procedures : (Ibid., p. 94.

First, the lesson is divided into several parts, then the teacher prepares a set of questions about each part.

The teacher opens the door for dialogue and discussion on a topic, where he leads the learners to reach the required information.

The teacher throws some questions to the learners and asks them to answer them, as the learners ' answers lead to reaching the required information.

In a manner that leads learners through questions to the ideas of the lesson and their sequence without deviating from its goals.

" Jaradat et al. (2008)" adds a number of classroom procedures that can be performed by the teacher, which are as follows:

Re-evaluate the points of view during the discussion, indicate how relevant they are to the topic.

To arouse the interest of students and motivate them to think.

The definition of the conclusion and final conclusions (Izzat Jaradat et al., 2008, p. 99

Based on this, the teacher may play various classroom roles through the dialogue process, sometimes as a discussion Director, another as an facilitator, and a third time as a referee, the purpose of these roles is to help learners think critically, discover facts, acquire the right information, and compare them.

In order for these roles to be successfully embodied, the teacher himself should have basic skills, most notably communication, management, encouragement and motivation skills, and above all, he should be convinced of the learners ' abilities and his role in the development of these abilities.

Among the factors that contribute to increasing the effectiveness of the method of dialogue and discussion and achieving its goals are the following:

The purpose of the discussion should be clear in the mind of the teacher and the minds of the learners.

The teacher should use well-formulated, clear and specific questions, each of which revolves around one idea so that the learners' thinking is not distracted.

Ensure that a few learners do not dominate the discussion, by monopolizing the answer to most questions.

Ensure that order is achieved inside the classroom during the discussion, and that noise, collective answers, interruptions, and other distracting factors do not occur.

survey method:

"The drunkard" (1989) reminds that this method is considered one of the important, effective and contemporary teaching methods in social studies, because the learner is the fulcrum of events and activities; he is placed in a position that requires deep thinking, cooperation and guidance from the teacher to reach the desired goals (Radina Youssef et al., 2005, P. 100).

The role of the teacher in the survey method:

The teacher in this way bases his role on guidance, guidance and participation; this certainly means abandoning his traditional role of conveying ready-made information to the learner and providing him with all the answers.

The role of the teacher in the survey process can be summarized as the following classroom procedures:

To give learners complete freedom to express their thoughts without restrictions.

To ensure that the learners know the previous requirements.

It involves asking concepts related to the topic of the lesson in the form of a question that is looking for an answer or a problem that requires a solution.

Analyze the problem and present it in the form of interesting questions.

The processing of the certain means required by the implementation of the class position.

The task is to identify the activities or experiences that the educational situation requires.

Developing strategies to address differences in learners' perspectives.

Provide timely advice and guidance, help to those who request it.

To evaluate the results and apply them in New similar situations.

One of the main elements that contribute to the activation of the survey method is the following:
Exploiting the learner's motivation to be an explorer as the center of effectiveness and activity in the educational-learning situation.

Work on linking previous experiences with the experiences to be discovered through suggestions or direct questions.

Providing the appropriate atmosphere that helps the investigation, by establishing the teaching position based on understanding the meanings and knowing the semantics of the pillars of the problems that are being raised or discussed

To ensure the correctness of intuition or guessing among learners; it works to form the idea and make it concrete within the scope of correct thinking that leads to the discovery of the solution, guessing is the penultimate step to discover the correct solution.

Helping the learner on the correct application; that is, helping him to correct the course of his thinking to neglect incorrect attempts, and the correct solution should be supported in the learner's mind through many examples and exercises.

Thus, relying on the survey method makes the learner have a great deal of independence and self-reliance, and he can use the skills he has acquired in the next steps leading to creativity.

The method of solving problems:

It is defined as a teaching method based on raising a problem that interests students, impresses them and pushes them to think, study and search for a scientific solution to this problem.

The use of the problem-solving method in teaching enhances the school's relationship with the environment in which the learner lives, and makes the curriculum a useful social function, because this method will make the learner more able to face problems, and seek to find appropriate solutions, relying on its own activity, by linking science to work and the integration of thought with reality, and that this method enables the teacher to turn all study topics into a problem that arouses the attention of students and pulls them to the classroom .

And John Dewey pointed out five steps to solve the problem: "

The feeling of having a problem.

Identify the problem.

Collect facts and information related to the problem.

Come up with hypotheses that are temporary solutions to the problem.

Test the validity of the proposed solutions or hypotheses.

The role of the teacher in the way of solving problems:

Both "Obeidat et al." (2005) and "Mohammed al-Qudah et al." (2006) touched on the role of the teacher in developing the method of solving problems by implementing a set of classroom procedures as follows:

The teacher determines the skills and knowledge that learners need to conduct research, survey and reconnaissance.

It identifies the initial results and concepts that learners acquire as a result of their research.

He teaches them models for solving problems that will benefit them in the future.

He distributes roles.

It helps learners to identify the references required to conduct the research.

He monitors the progress of learners and intervenes to support them whenever required.

It evaluates the performance of learners.

The teacher then intervenes in the selection of the problem, determining its initial formulation, taking into account its connection with the needs of learners and the school curriculum.

Among the things that must be provided for the activation and success of the problem-solving method in teaching the educational material are the following:

The need for the educational material to be suitable for learning in a problem-solving style, as the nature of the material determines the method sometimes used in teaching.

-Determining the educational goals and the main skills contained in the educational material in order to be clear in the mind of the teacher before embarking on training or teaching them.

Determine the necessary and sufficient time to solve the problem, given the importance of the time spent on the solution and the indicators of the abilities of learners.

The teacher studies the problem and solves it individually in order to determine the way or ways in which the problem may be solved, and through this he can determine the time required for the solution.

Determining the criteria for evaluating solutions, whether chronologically, skillfully, or through what goals have been achieved.

Identify some circumstances, guidelines and instructions that work to help learners in facilitating important charges and solving them of the problem.

brainstorming method:

This method is used to produce creative ideas from learners in solving a specific problem; that is, putting the mind in a state of excitement and readiness to think in all directions, to generate as many ideas as possible about a problem or topic, and this requires removing all obstacles to thought to disclose all its findings.

Brainstorming was divided into three basic stages, each of which must be performed accurately to ensure its success, as follows: (Fatima Mahmoud al-Zayat, 2009, pp. 179-180).

The first stage: clarifying the problem and analyzing it into its initial elements, then tabulating it in order to present it for discussion in the idea generation session.

The second stage : the session leader explains how to work to the individuals participating in the session:

A-avoid evaluating the participants ' thoughts.

B-accept any idea, even if it is imaginary or imaginary.

C-submit as many ideas as possible.

D-keenness to follow the ideas of others, build on them and find links between them in various ways to reach creative ideas.

The third stage: the stage of evaluating ideas and testing them in practice, and this stage may take a long time until other new ideas appear that can be useful

The role of the teacher in the method of brainstorming

The teacher works on the configuration of the classroom and arranges the chairs in a circle.

The teacher demonstrates the basic principles on which the brainstorming session is based.

The teacher puts the problem in front of the students and carefully clarifies it.

The teacher asks each group to choose her coordinator or a writer who will record what is presented at the session, so that it is acceptable to the students or sufficiently familiar with the topic of the problem.

After the ideas are discussed, the teacher classifies them into, for example, viable ideas and non-viable ideas, and then the ideas that won the majority of the votes of the participating students are adopted.

The teacher comments on the ideas circulating to solve the problem... In partnership with the students, he gives from one to five marks for each idea that the students discuss, and the idea with the highest mark is the best to solve the problem.

Among the important elements that contribute to the activation and success of the brainstorming process are the following:.

Clarity of the problem under research and related information and knowledge among the participants and the leader of the activity before the storm session.

Clarity of the principles and rules of work and adherence to them by all.

The experience of the activity leader, his seriousness and conviction of the value of brainstorming as one of the cognitive directions in stimulating creativity, in addition to his role in maintaining the enthusiasm of the participants in an atmosphere of reassurance, relaxation and launch.

project method:

William Kilpatrick defined it as: "problem work, which is carried out in its entirety in its natural environment, which is of two types; a group project involving all the students of the class and an individual project carried out by each student alone.

The role of the teacher in the project method:

The role of the teacher in the implementation of classroom actions of this method can be summarized as follows:

The teacher should improve the choice of projects; where they are rich in their elements, clear in their goals, and meet the needs of learners.

The teacher participates in the discussion sessions in an advisory and guiding capacity, and being the owner of experience that can be used.

The teacher plays the role of guidance and guidance, and determines individual criteria that help learners to process criticism and judge their completed projects.

Accordingly, the project method needs special preparation for the teacher, where he trains on supervision, follow-up and guidance, and to provide learners with a correct approach to thinking, and a successful method of planning, implementing and evaluating projects.

It is true that students participate in the selection, planning, implementation and evaluation of projects, but the teacher should prevent the loss of time and effort, and aim their work towards their goals whenever necessary.

There are several factors contributing to the activation and success of the project method, they can be summarized as follows:

1. the nature of the submitted projects should correspond to the students ' stage of study.
2. ensure the students ' ability to implement the chosen project.
3. providing the appropriate supplies and Means for the completion of projects.
4. the need to follow up projects, and the level of their development.

5. saving the available time to follow up projects.

Conclusion

Based on the above, it can be said that teaching methods contribute significantly to the achievement of educational goals; because it is they who determine the appropriate classroom roles of the teacher in the implementation of the educational-learning process, and it is they who determine the means to be used and the pedagogical and classroom procedures to be performed to activate and make the educational situation successful.

Therefore, the teacher should have wide flexibility in choosing the teaching method that he considers appropriate within the framework of the previous criteria, provided that this method attracts the attention of learners and makes them want to learn the subject and enhance their participation in the learning process on the one hand, and achieve the desired goals on the other.

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